
End-of-Life Decisions for Wind Farms:
An Opportunity for Climate Action and for Energy Communities

**Report: Community Risk Aversion Measures from China,
France, Ireland and USA**
Work Package 7.3

Month 42/48, Aug 2025

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October 6, 2025

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Suggested Citation: Delnatte, M. & Deeney, P. (2025) Report: Community Risk Aversion Measures from China, France, Ireland and USA. Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/records/13995914>, Accessed (date). DOI

Executive Summary

The Wind Value research project seeks to estimate a financial valuation for onshore wind farms in Ireland. It will develop decision support tools which will assist wind farm managers in deciding between decommissioning, re-powering, and life-extension for the end-of-life of a wind farm. This research will also assist local communities who may be interested in buying part or all of their local wind farm.

In this report the risk appetites of participants in China, France, Ireland and USA are compared. We find that the lowest risk appetite is displayed by French participants, and that Chinese women have the largest difference between their self reported risk appetite (very low) and their measured risk appetite (low).

This publication has emanated from research conducted with the financial support of Taighde Éireann – [Research Ireland](#) under Grant number IRC*21/PATH-A/9348.

1 Introduction

The Wind Value research project aims to assist communities who wish to invest in wind energy. Part of this requires an understanding of the risk appetite and risk aversion of those who may wish to invest. In this report the risk aversion and risk appetite from four groups of participants in different countries is compared. It is important to understand this topic as any investment vehicle aimed at non-professional investors, must offer as low-risk a product as possible, and must understand the risk appetite of investors. This report does not claim to survey the risk appetites of four countries, but to give an insight into the methods which can be used even at a small scale.

2 Method

2.1 Background

This research builds on the studies of Annarita Colasante and Luca Riccetti ¹ which used a questionnaire to assess the risk aversion of participants. This method was used in earlier Wind Value reports by *Baxter et al. (2023)* and *Chen & Deeney (2024)* to assess risk aversion for small samples of Irish and Chinese participants respectively. Here the sample was extended to include additional Irish participants (collected by Dorcas Mikindani), and new participants from France (collected by Marceau Delnatte) and USA (collected by Peter Deeney).

2.2 The Questionnaire

The questionnaire is divided into two parts: the first being the questions on financial risk taken from the Colasante and Riccetti (2020, 2021), and the second part being a mix of Wind Value-specific questions and demographic questions.

The risk attitude questionnaire was distributed to American and French students, and Irish and Chinese communities using the collectors’ networks (and translated into the respective nationalities’ languages). This report will detail the analysis of the answers received, their implications, and the correlation between different indicators.

For the second part, questions include rating the likelihood of investing in wind farms, the amounts that one would invest, as well as the demographic inquiries.

Nationality	USA	France	Ireland	China	Total
Initial Responses	34	34	108	68	240
Final Number	34	34	95	61	220
Questions	US-Q	FR -Q	IE-Q	CN-Q	
Answers	US-A	FR-A	IE-A	CN-A	

Table 1: Number of responses obtained per nationality, and links to the Zenodo pages for copies of the questionnaires and responses.

As will be explained later, some responses were ruled out, either on the basis of a low *rationality score* or because of a lack of answered questions.

2.3 Research Questions

- RQ1: Is there a non-zero correlation between risk aversion and self reported risk appetite in the participants?

¹*Colasante & Riccetti (2020)* Risk aversion, prudence and temperance: It is a matter of gap between moments, Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance and *Colasante & Riccetti (2021)* Financial and non-financial risk attitudes: What does it matter? Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance

- RQ2: Is there a difference between USA, China, France and Ireland for mean of the risk aversion and risk loving scores?
- RQ3: Is there a difference between male and female participants' mean risk aversion and risk loving scores within USA, China, France and Ireland?
- RQ4: Is there a non-zero correlation between risk aversion (tested and self reported) and the likelihood towards wind farm investment?

2.4 Scoring Method

Following Colasante & Riccetti (2020, 2021), we calculate a risk-aversion score for each participant. A response to the questionnaire is given 1 point for every answer that is the same as the "*Risk averse option*" in Table 2 which is taken from Colasante and Riccatti (2020). The questions may be found in Section 4.

Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Risk averse option	B	A	B	B	B	B	A	X	B	X	B	B	B
Alternate propensity option	A	B	A	A	A	A	B	A	X	A	X	A	A

Table 2: "Financial risk scores": responses gain 1 point towards their Risk Aversion score. Questions with "X" are not used for the computation of the score.

The risk aversion scores are associated with lower second and fourth moments, and a higher third moment. The first moment, being the average gain/loss, was the same for both A/B options every question, except question zero.

Additionally, we also have a self-assessed *risk-loving score* (SARL), where participants ranked themselves from 0 (totally risk-averse) to 10 (totally risk-loving). From that, we can obtain a simple *self-assessed risk-aversion score* (SARA) and an *error* value with the following logic:

Risk-averse (RA) score	x
Self-assessed risk-loving (SARL) score	y
Self-assessed risk-aversion (SARA) score	11 - y
Error (SARA score - RA score)	(11 - y) - x

Table 3: Scoring Method

Note that the SARL score is on a scale from 0 to 10 while the risk-averse score is from 0 to 11. We should then have resized the SARL score to this range by multiplying it by a factor of 11/10. However, we have not done this for two reasons:(i) No participant scored 0 on the RA score, essentially making it a 1-11 score, which is the same range as the SARA score; and (ii) Resizing the SARL to 0-11 makes the *Error* score not an integer, rendering analysis of the values more complicated.

We believe that these reasons justify our choice of variables.

2.5 Data Cleaning

As shown in Table 1, some answers have not been considered in the final data analysis, for two main reasons :

- Some participants didn't answer enough questions thus making their data irrelevant to analyze;
- Some participants scored below 3 out of 5 on the *rationality score* detailed by Colasante and Riccetti.

The *rationality score* of one's answers is defined as ranging from 0 to 5 ; it is calculated on a few questions, and if the answers chosen present an irrational behavior.

For instance, choosing Option A to Question 0 (participating in a lottery with positive expected gain and no loss) adds 1 point to the rationality score ; choosing Option B gives 0. The details of this score are explained in Colasante and Riccetti (2020). Colasante and Riccetti (2021) argued in their paper that answers scoring below 3 should not be considered, as they don't showcase a logical enough answer selection to be analyzed.

After the screening of such "irrational" responses, and those with too few questions answered, a total of 20 participants were removed.

3 Results

3.1 Self-Assessed Risk Behavior

The first question we will answer is whether we see a correlation between the risk aversion score as measured by the answers to the questionnaire, and the self-assessed risk-loving score.

Figure 1: SARL and RA scores scatter plot

As the scatter plot of Figure 1 shows, a trend of correlation seems to exist between the tested score and the risk-loving score obtained from participants themselves. We obtain a correlation value of $-0,3842$ and a t-value of $-6,1309$, which gives us a p-value of below 0,000 for both two-tailed and one-tailed test. (Note that the comma indicates a decimal point, following French usage.)

A Fisher z-test allows us to test the correlation value for significance. Our null hypothesis and our alternative hypothesis are

$$H_0 : p = 0,25 \quad \text{and} \quad H_a : p > 0,25$$

using these values, we can find that our correlation obtains a z-value of $2,2039$, which validates our alternative hypothesis of a non-zero correlation.

Because of the linear nature between the SARL and SARA score, we can conclude that there is a significant, moderate, correlation between the tested (RA) and self-assessed risk aversion (SARA) score.

3.2 Demographic Study

The following sections will focus on the risk-aversion questions, their relation to demographics, and comparing our results with the Colasante & Riccetti.

The first result we obtain is the total score distribution, ranging from 0 (totally risk-loving) to 11 (totally risk-averse). In our pool of answers, no single participant scored a 0, which is in line with Colasante and Riccetti's results. 0.42% of their answers obtained a score of 0, which in our case would be 0.924 participants on average. Note, each axis in the following graphs will be from 1 to 11.

Figure 2: Score Distribution Bar Graph

RA Score	# of Responses
1	3
2	5
3	9
4	10
5	26
6	37
7	48
8	45
9	25
10	12
11	4

Table 4: Total Score Distribution

Figure 2 and Table 4 showcase the distribution of scores in the answers we obtain from our participants. In Figure 2, we also have the score distribution of Colasante & Riccetti’s study. We can see that our distribution is skewed towards a higher risk-aversion average (towards a score of 11) compared to theirs. As we will see after, it might be a result of our participants’ demographic distribution.

As Table 1 shows, participants of this study are not distributed uniformly between the different nationalities studied.

3.2.1 Analysis of the risk-aversion score

Figure 3: Score Distribution Graph of each Nationality

Score	USA	France	Ireland	China
1	0	0	2	1
2	0	0	1	4
3	3	0	4	2
4	1	0	3	6
5	7	2	12	5
6	12	5	10	10
7	4	4	25	15
8	5	10	20	10
9	0	10	9	6
10	2	2	7	1
11	0	1	2	1
Mean	6,1	7,9	6,9	6,3
Std Dev	1,6586	1,4218	2,0421	2,1451

Table 5: Total score distribution per nationality

The above tables and graph showcase the score distribution for each nationality, with the values of the graph being proportional to the population size of each nationality. As we can see, the distribution varies between the different nationalities.

The first two major observations from the above data are that US and Chinese participants seem to score lower than the other nationalities, while French participants score much higher than the others on risk aversion, with the Irish participants in the middle. In their analysis, Colasante & Riccetti found "*European subjects more risk averse in financial choices*", and we observe a similar result here, with France and Ireland having the lowest average scores.

In our study, more than 57% of participants are European, while only 15% are from North America. Colasante & Riccetti did not specify the number of participants from each nationality in their papers, but if they had a higher proportion of North American answers, it would explain the difference in our distribution compared to theirs. A higher number of US participants would skew our distribution towards lower risk-aversion values and make it look more similar to C&R's distribution.

	FRA	IRE	CN
USA	4,7887	2,2295	0,4487
FRA	/	3,1308	4,4018
IRE	/	/	1,7664

(a) t-values of the unpaired t-tests between the means of two nationalities

	FRA	IRE	CN
USA	$\leq 0,001$	0,029	0,655
FRA	/	0,002	$\leq 0,001$
IRE	/	/	0,078

(b) p-values of the unpaired t-tests between the means of two nationalities

Table 6: Results of difference of means using unpaired t-tests between the scores of each nationality

We have further analyzed the difference between the results of different nationalities by performing an unpaired Student's t-test between each pair of nationalities. From the results above, we can conclude the following:

- The French score distribution is hugely significantly different from all of the others;
- The US score distribution is significantly different from the European ones, but not from the Chinese distribution;
- The Chinese and Irish distributions exhibits differences, but the null hypothesis can't be rejected.

3.2.2 Analysis of the self-assessed risk-loving score

Figure 4: SARL distribution graph of each nationality

Score	USA	France	Ireland	China
0	0	0	0	0
1	0	0	2	5
2	0	10	9	3
3	8	10	18	7
4	3	4	14	10
5	6	2	14	14
6	8	5	17	10
7	5	3	12	5
8	1	0	4	3
9	0	0	2	1
10	2	0	0	2
Mean	5,4	3,7	4,7	4,8
Standard Deviation	1,8881	1,6857	1,8817	2,1069

Table 7: Total SARL score distribution per nationality

	FRA	IRE	CN
USA	3,7200	1,4102	1,2427
FRA	/	3,0714	2,6665
IRE	/	/	0,0061

(a) t-values of the unpaired t-tests between the means of two nationalities

	FRA	IRE	CN
USA	$\leq 0,001$	0,164	0,218
FRA	/	0,003	0,009
IRE	/	/	0,995

(b) p-values of the unpaired t-tests between the means of two nationalities

Table 8: Results of unpaired t-tests between the SARL score of each nationality

The figure and tables above show us the distribution of the SARL score for each nationality as well as the unpaired t-test values between each pair of nationalities. We can find similar results to Section 3.2.1, although with some differences:

- The French SARL score distribution is hugely significantly different from all of the others;
- Although the US SARL score distribution looks different to the others, it is only significantly different to France’s distribution;
- The Chinese and Irish distributions don’t exhibit any difference.

3.2.3 Analysis of the error score

Figure 5: Error distribution graph of each nationality

Score	USA	France	Ireland	China
Median	-0,6111	-0,8750	-1,0952	-0,6667
Mean	-0,4848	-0,6471	-0,6522	-0,0833
Standard Deviation	2,0935	1,9830	2,1860	2,4926

Table 9: Error score data per nationality

The above graph and table show us the distribution of the error score ($Error = SARA - RA$) for each nationality. In our model, a participant getting a negative error score means they scored higher in risk aversion than what they rated themselves. We will call that "*overconfidence*", and the reverse "*under-confidence*".

As we can see, at least 20% of participants in each nationality correctly rank their risk aversion. On the other hand, the median and average show that most of them present overconfidence in their risk-loving behavior. Otherwise, the different distributions showcase similarly looking skewed bell curves with their peaks at 0 and a skewness towards negative values.

3.2.4 Conclusion on the demographic RA and SARL analysis

From the analysis we have, the following conclusions have been made :

- The French distribution showcases the most significant differences with the others, presenting a high risk aversion in both true score and self-assessed score.
- The US distribution displays a higher risk-loving behavior than the others, although it is only slightly significant.
- The Chinese and Irish distributions are not significantly different from each other.

3.3 Demographic and Gender Study

In this section, we will analyze the different scores when genders are taken into account. Because of the answers received in this study, we will only analyze the answers from participants who defined themselves as men or women (210 of the 224 participants).

3.3.1 General gender analysis

Figure 6: RA score distribution graph of each gender

Score	Women	Men
1	1	1
2	1	3
3	3	6
4	2	6
5	15	10
6	19	18
7	17	28
8	19	23
9	13	8
10	4	8
11	2	2
Average	6,8646	6,6930
Standard deviation	1,8909	2,0780

Table 10: Error score data per gender

To determine if there is a significant difference in the two data sets, we performed both a correlation significance test and a Student's t-test.

	Student (difference in means)	Correlation
Value	0,1716	0,0428
t-value	0,6261	0,6181
p-value	0,532	0,527

Table 11: Difference of means and non-zero Correlation tests

As we can see, both tests indicate no significant difference whatsoever between the RA

scores of women and those of men. *"Risk aversion, [...]"(2020)* mentions the significance of disparity between male and female participants. Colasante & Riccetti don't seem to have found a significant difference in male and female answers for their financial risk aversion score. If we assume that we can compare our men and women results to their male and female ones, we then have the same analysis as them.

	US(M)	US(F)	FR(M)	FR(F)	IR(M)	IR(F)	CN(M)	CN(F)
Average	6,000	6,308	8,000	7,727	6,889	7,020	6,029	6,409
Std. Dev.	1,773	1,435	1,319	1,601	2,183	1,838	2,093	2,146
Sample size	21	13	23	11	36	50	34	22
t-value	0,554		0,491		0,293		0,653	
p-value	0,584		0,630		0,770		0,517	

Table 12: RA score data per gender and nationality

Table 12 shows that when comparing the scores of the two genders for each nationality, we still see no significant differences between men's and women's scores.

3.3.2 SABL and error scores among gender

Figure 7: SABL score distribution graph of each gender

	Women	Men
Sample size	93	113
Mean	4,3	5,1
Standard deviation	1.8450	2,0202

Table 13: SABL score data per gender

	Student (difference in means)	Correlation
Value	0,7982	-0,2012
t-value	2,9598	-2,9266
p-value	0,003	0,004

Table 14: t-values and p-values of the correlation and Student's t test

Studying the SARL score paints quite a different picture to the RA score. The distributions visually look different, and both the Student and correlation t-tests confirm the difference. We can add to this difference with the data on the error score:

Figure 8: Error score distribution graph of each gender

	Women	Men
Sample size	93	113
Average	-0,1720	-0,7788
Standard deviation	1,9980	2,3071

Table 15: RA score data per gender

	Student (difference in means)	Correlation
Value	0,6067	0,1376
t-value	2,0221	1,9796
p-value	0,044	0,049

Table 16: T-values and P-values of the correlation and Student's test

The SARL and error score, unlike the RA score, show a significant difference between men and women. Despite scoring similar results on the test, men in this study have a tendency to judge themselves as more risk-loving than women. The correlation between error and gender indicates that there is somewhat a bias for men to rate themselves as more risk-loving than what they score, while women are less subject to this error.

3.3.3 Results in regard of demography

SARL	US(M)	US(W)	FR(M)	FR(W)	IR(M)	IR(W)	CH(M)	CH(W)
Average	5,6190	4,9167	3,9130	3,3636	4,9714	4,7083	5,6765	3,5000
Std. Dev.	1,7314	2,0599	1,7424	1,4938	2,0069	1,7073	1,9811	1,6720
Pop Size	21	12	23	11	35	48	34	22
t-value	0,9970		0,9494		0,6275		4,4197	

Table 17: SARL score data per gender and nationality

With this data, we notice a very skewed result. Among the US, French and Irish demographic, the difference in the SARL score is not significant (the t-values would have to be $\geq 1,7$). However, in the Chinese demographic, the difference is significantly prominent, having a p-value $\leq 0,001$.

SARL	US(M)	US(W)	FR(M)	FR(W)	IR(M)	IR(W)	CH(M)	CH(W)
Average	-0,619	-0,250	-0,913	-0,091	-0,857	-0,750	-0,706	1,091
Std. Dev.	2,179	2,006	2,255	1,136	2,658	1,695	2,154	2,467
Pop Size	21	12	23	11	35	48	34	22
t-value	0,493		1,413		0,209		2,796	

Table 18: Error score data per gender and nationality

The Error score data show a very similar result, where the Chinese scores are the only ones presenting a significant difference (here, the p-value is 0,008). It seems that the disparity seen in the overall results are mostly due to the Chinese scores.

On these two scores, we can notice several interesting facts:

- The French and Chinese women have a very similar average and standard deviation regarding the SARL score.
- However, the French men's SARL score data doesn't differ as much from their female counterpart as the Chinese men's data do for their counterpart.
- Chinese men have the highest average SARL score of our population while Chinese women have the lowest.
- Chinese women rate themselves as way more risk-averse than they really are, showing the highest absolute error score.

3.3.4 Conclusion on the gendered demographic analysis

Combining the gender and demographic study paints a better picture on the results we had. The first result we obtained is that there are no real difference in the tested risk-aversion scores between men and women from the same nationality. Meaning the differences between different nationalities in the RA scores are driven by sociocultural elements.

Meanwhile, the results of the self-assessed and error scores present a higher disparity between women and men, that we initially studied globally. However, we noticed that the disparities are

not equally distributed in our total population. Indeed, While US, French and Irish answers did not present significant differences between men and women of these nationalities, the Chinese presented heavily parted results in their SARL and error scores.

3.4 Links with Wind Value Questions

In our version of the questionnaire, several questions regarding wind farms and investment were appended to the risk questionnaire. Among these questions were the following:

- Max Inv: If you were to consider investing in a wind farm project with an attractive rate of return, what is the maximum amount you would be willing to invest?
- Min ROI: If you were to consider investing in a wind farm project, what is the minimum rate of return you would expect to receive on your investment annually?
- Likeliness: Given your knowledge about the benefits of using wind energy, how likely are you to consider investing in a wind farm project?

The first two questions were scaled from 0 to 3, with 0 being considered as the most risk-averse answer (no investment no matter what), and 3 being the most risk-loving answer (minimum ROI and maximum investment). The third question was scaled from 0, being "very unlikely to invest" to 4 being "very likely to invest". The answers of these questions were tested for correlation against the RA and SARL scores.

	RA Score			SARL Score		
	Max Inv.	Min ROI	Likeliness	Max Inv.	Min ROI	Likeliness
DoF	213	216	218	208	211	213
Correlation	0,0005	-0,0937	-0,2631	0,1421	0,1098	0,2524
t-value	0,008	1,383	4,027	2,071	1,604	3,808

Table 19: Table of correlation between RA and SARL score to Wind Value related questions

In bold we have the correlations where their t-values are above the minimum for a $\leq 0,05$ p-value. As we can see, the two most significant correlations are both the scores against the likeliness of investment. We have also a significant enough correlation between the SARL score and Maximum Investment, but the correlation value is low and isn't strong against non null hypothesis. Let's then focus on the results concerning Likeliness.

Figure 9: RA - Likelihood of investment scatter plot

Figure 10: SARL - Likelihood of investment scatter plot

The p-values of both correlations are $\leq 0,001$. It may seem evident that this link is somewhat significant, since it is in essence another self-assessed rating of one's risk-loving behavior. However, this question is specifically related to wind farms and not risk in general. We can further our analysis by looking into the correlation values of each nationality in the same manner.

Test	RA - Likeliness				SARL - Likeliness			
	US	FR	IR	CN	US	FR	IR	CN
Nationality	US	FR	IR	CN	US	FR	IR	CN
Correlation	-0,1563	-0,1052	-0,1570	-0,2819	0,1566	0,0289	0,3209	0,2157
t-Value	-0,934	-0,621	-1,569	-2,392	0,936	0,169	3,486	1,767

Table 20: Correlation values of RA and SARL Score to Likeliness of investment, per nationality

Table 20 shows another layer to this correlation. We see that the strongest correlations are from China and Ireland, for RA-Likeliness and SARL-Likeliness respectively. China’s correlation coefficient between SARL score and Likeliness of investment is also technically above the threshold for a p-value $\leq 0,05$ for one-tailed-ness, but not for two-tailed-ness ; while Ireland’s coefficient for RA-Likeliness is just below the one-tailed-ness threshold.

We can speculate that these results stem from the cultural and societal aspects regarding wind turbines. Ireland has a strong wind farm program and grid, while China is quickly becoming a wind superpower.

4 Conclusions

Through our results, we have been able to draw answers for all of our principal research questions.

- RQ1 *Is there a non-zero correlation between risk aversion and self reported risk appetite in the participants?*

Yes, there is a correlation value of $-0,3842$ (indicating that people that rate themselves as more risk-loving score lower on the risk-aversion test). The coefficient holds up in a Fisher z-test, indicating a strong correlation. The calculation below Figure 1 showed us that the correlation indicates it is significantly stronger than a value of 0,25.

- RQ2 *Is there a difference between USA, China, France and Ireland for mean of the risk aversion and risk loving scores?*

Our result showed strong differences between the four nationalities we have on several indicators. Most notably, France’s distributions in both RA and SARL scores are very different from all of the others, having the highest RA mean score and lowest SARL score. The US seems to exhibit the opposite, having both lowest RA score and highest SARL score, however the Student tests show that both distributions are not significantly different enough from Ireland or China. The error score for all countries present similar-looking distributions as well as close medians, average and variance.

- RQ3 *Is there a difference between male and female participants’ mean risk aversion and risk loving scores within USA, China, France and Ireland?*

As previous research suggested, there is no difference between men and women regarding the risk-aversion test scores. Both distributions are very similar, and both Student and correlation test proved no significant distinction between them. However, the SARL and error scores show a different story, both indicating dissimilarities between men and women. When also considering demographics, we have been able to conclude that the disparities are hugely driven by the Chinese answers, as they present a large gap between male and female answers.

- RQ4 *Is there a non-zero correlation between risk aversion (tested and self reported) and wind farm investment likeliness?*

There is a correlation between the likeliness of investment in wind farms and both RA and SARL scores. The correlations seem primarily driven by Irish and Chinese answers,

which might be due to both countries' strong wind development and familiarity with the technology.

The main results for the Wind Value research project are that people are generally very good at estimating their own risk appetite, and that there is no evidence of a significant difference in risk attitude between women and men. For Wind Value this means that community investment does not need to adjust for error in non-professional risk self-assessment and that there is no need to adjust for gender.

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Copy of Questionnaire

Q0

You have the opportunity to participate in a lottery in which you have an equal chance (50%) of winning €100 or winning nothing. There is no fee to take part.

Option A: you participate in the lottery

OR

Option B: you do not participate.

Q1

You can choose between two investments:

Option A: offers an equal chance (50%) to gain €5 or €15

OR

Option B: offers you a certain gain of €10.

Q2

Suppose you have been fined and you have the opportunity to choose between two alternatives.

Option A: pay a fine of €10

OR

Option B: have an equal chance (50%) of paying either €5 or €15.

Q3

You may decide to participate to a lottery in which you have an equal chance (50%) to gain or lose €5000.

Option A: you will take part in the lottery

OR

Option B: you do not participate.

Q4

You may decide to take part in a lottery in which you have the an equal chance (50%) to gain or lose €5.

Option A: you will take part in the lottery

OR

Option B: you do not participate.

Q5

Option A: you have an equal chance (50%) of winning or losing €5,000

OR

Option B: you have an equal chance (50%) of winning or losing €5.

Q6

Option A: you have an equal chance (50

OR

Option B: you a sure gain of €10,000.

Q7

Option A: pay a fine of €10,000

OR

Option B: have an equal chance (50%) of paying either €5,000 or €15,000.

Q8

Option A: you have one chance in a million to win one million euro

OR

Option B: gain €1 for sure.

Q9

Option A: You have a on in one thousand chance (0.1%) of losing €1,000, otherwise you lose nothing (zero)

OR

Option B: pay €1 for sure.

Q10

Option A: You have a one in 100 chance (1%) of winning €10,000 and 99 in 100 (99%) of losing €101

OR

Option B: An equal chance (50%) of winning €1000 or losing €1000.

Q11

Option A: 1% chance to lose €10,000 and 99% chance to win €101

OR

Option B: equal chance (50%) to win €1000 or lose €1000.

Q12

Option A: You have an equal chance (33%) to gain, €0 or €5000 or €10,000

OR

Option B: You have an equal chance (25%) to gain, €0 or €2100 or €7900 or €10,000.

Q13

Option A: You have an Equal chance (33%) of, €0 or €5000 or -€5000 (negative number means losing)

OR

Option B: You have an Equal chance (25%) of, €2900 or €5000 or -€2900 or -€5000.

Socio-Demographic Questions

Q14 How do you see yourself: are you in general a person who takes risk or do you try to evade risk? Please self-grade your choice between 0 (I do not take risk at all) to 10 (I love to take risks). 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Q15 If you were to consider investing in a windfarm project, what is the minimum rate of return you would expect to receive on your investment annually?

0%-5%

5%-10%

More than 10%

The return on investment is irrelevant, I would not invest in a wind farm project.

Q16 If you were to consider investing in a windfarm project with an attractive rate of return, what is the maximum amount you would be willing to invest?

€1-€20,000

€20,000-€50,000

More than €50,000

Nothing, I would not invest in a wind farm project

Q17 Approximately, what is the distance from your home to the nearest wind turbine?

Less than 1km

1km-5km

5km-10km

More than 10km

Q18 What is the main deciding factor in your choice of electricity provider?

Price

Renewable Energy

Combination of Price and Renewable Energy

Q19 Given your knowledge about the benefits of using wind energy, how likely are you to consider investing in a wind farm project?

Very likely

Somewhat likely

Neither likely nor unlikely

Somewhat unlikely

Very unlikely **Q20** What option below do you believe most accurately describes the purpose of wind farms?

Profitable Business

Climate Change Solution

Electricity Generation

Q21 Are you aware of the EU Targets for Reducing Emissions by 2030?

Not Aware

Somewhat Aware

Very Aware

Q22 What is your age?

18 - 24

25 - 34

35 - 44

45 - 54

55 - 64

65 - 74

75 +

Q23 What is your gender? Write your answer 26. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

Primary

Secondary

Post Secondary

University or College